

LIVING WITH COMPOSITES - DAMAGE, DURABILITY AND REPAIR ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses a number of issues that affect the life cycle costs of composite structures including mechanical damage, environmental degradation and the design and implementation of composite repairs. The origin and frequency of impact damage and delamination experienced by the CF-18 aircraft are reviewed and some of the difficulties in accurately assessing the need for repair are discussed. Several different forms of environmental degradation that have been observed to occur with composites on aircraft are also described. Next, some of the factors limiting the effectiveness and application of adhesively bonded patches are addressed and the key parameters controlling the successful repair of delaminations by resin injection are related to the interlaminar fracture of the rebonded surfaces. A few of the technologies that have been developed in Canada to meet the maintenance and support requirements of composites in systems are also described. Finally, some of the life cycle issues that are as yet unresolved, as well as those that are likely to arise in the future, are identified.

INTRODUCTION

While most of the research and development activity related to composite materials tends to be either fundamental in nature or directed towards new materials, processes and applications, there is also a significant effort being expended on addressing problems that arise once they are in use. This is not to say that composite materials have performed unsatisfactorily in service or have required a drastic change in the way in which equipment that is constructed from them must be looked after. Far from it. Not only have composites allowed designers to expand the performance envelope of a wide variety of equipment and structures, from sporting goods to advanced technology aircraft but they are also proving that they have the potential to substantially reduce the enormous costs currently associated with the corrosion and fatigue of metals. Nevertheless, any new material is likely to provide its own surprises, to respond to its operating environment in a manner different from that anticipated during design and to require its own unique solutions to everyday problems.

Important lessons can be learned by carefully analyzing any unexpected composites failures that do occur and providing feedback to designers, material suppliers and those involved in composites' manufacturing and fabrication. For structural applications, new technologies are being developed to detect and characterize the damage experienced by composites, to assess the structural significance of that damage and to design and implement temporary and/or permanent repairs. Ancillary maintenance and logistics operations such as paint removal and the storage and inventorying of repair materials are also being modified to accommodate the different characteristics of composite materials.

This paper will attempt to identify the key factors affecting most of these life cycle issues and to indicate where further research and development activity would be worthwhile. Emphasis will be placed on problems that have affected us directly and on a few of the solutions that have been developed in Canada. Some of the supportability challenges that will have to be faced in the future as composite applications become more sophisticated and demanding will also be discussed.

MECHANICAL DAMAGE

Resistance to impact and the ability of a structure to tolerate impact damage when it does occur has long been recognized as one of the most critical aspects of composite design. With composite aircraft structures, impact damage is not only a structural integrity concern but can also be one of the leading causes for repair action. The F-18 (CF-18 in Canada), which has been in service since the early 80's and has 40% of its surface area made from carbon/epoxy skins having thicknesses that vary from under 2 mm to over 15 mm, has provided valuable data concerning the frequency and nature of impact damage. Fig. 1 shows the location of the composite structure on the CF-18.

Figure 1. Usage of carbon/epoxy on the CF-18.

The relatively thick (>5 mm) wing skins and vertical stabilizers are comprised of monolithic carbon/epoxy laminates (Hercules® AS/3501-6) mechanically fastened to the aluminum substructure, whereas the flight control surfaces and access doors and covers are made of relatively thin skins (<5 mm) of the same carbon/epoxy material adhesively bonded to aluminum honeycomb core. Almost all of the impact damage that has occurred has been found on the lightweight sandwich structure. Table 1 summarizes the origins and frequency of the impact damage that has been encountered. Infrequent causes of accidental damage have included a gust of wind blowing a

Table 1. Origins of impact damage to the CF-18 composite sandwich structure.

Cause of Damage - On the Ground	Cause of Damage - In Motion	Frequency
Contact with stand or ground equipment	Debris from weapon firing/release	more often
Contact with other part of AC during system check	Runway debris	
Dropped tool	Birdstrike	seldom
Improper use of tools (pry damage)	Lightning strike	
Accidental	Ricochet after strafing run	

table against the main landing gear doors and a fluorescent light tube falling from its fixture on the hangar ceiling. While it is up to the designer to decide on an appropriate level of resistance to these diverse impact threats, from a maintenance perspective it is the nature and size of the resulting damage and whether or not it requires repair, that is important. Typical damage, which appears as a dent on the surface, can involve broken fibres, delaminations, debonding of the skin from the core as well as crushing of the honeycomb. Assessment of the structural implications and long term consequences of this type of damage do not lend themselves particularly well to an analytical approach. This is because of the large number of possible failure modes and the interaction between these modes; eg. damage progression can take the form of fatigue cracking and corrosion of the plastically deformed aluminum, growth of both disbands in the adhesive and delaminations in the skin. Criteria on which repair/no repair decisions are made tend to be entirely empirical and are based on a limited amount of fatigue data (eg. fully reversed 3-point bending) generated with panels containing impact damage of different depths and diameters. Because of the many variables involved, eg skin thickness, lay-up, core density and strain level, use of the fatigue data tends to be, by necessity, quite conservative and as a result damage limits are very stringent. For example, on parts of the horizontal stabilator, negligible dents must have a depth of less than 0.4 mm and field repairable dents less than 1.27 mm. In spite of this, evidence to date indicates that this type of composite structure has required less maintenance than equivalent metallic structure. In Table 2 the number of faults reported and the maintenance required during the same time interval are compared

Table 2. Maintenance requirements for the CF-18 composite trailing edge flap compared to the metallic aileron.

	Trailing Edge Flap	Aileron
Number of Fault Reports	458	462
Total Person hours Expended	4265	7624
Number of Faults sent for Depot Level Maintenance	18	25

for the CF-18's carbon/epoxy trailing edge flaps and the adjacent metallic elevators. Unfortunately the maintenance data base from which this information was extracted was not set-up with composites in mind and only provides a general indication of the types of damage involved as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Comparison of damage modes between CF-18 aileron and trailing edge flap.

In contrast to the composite sandwich components, impact damage to the CF-18's monolithic composite structure has been relatively rare. The greater thickness and more compliant boundary conditions that result from the support given by the sub-structure (as opposed to honeycomb) appears to be sufficient to raise the damage threshold above that of most impacts. Of course one of the other major differences between the two types of structure is that in the latter, there may be internal delamination damage with little or no visible signs at the surface. As discussed below, the inspection of an entire aircraft wing for sub-surface damage is no trivial task and hence no thorough search for non-visible delamination damage has yet been attempted. Nevertheless, no structural problems associated with impact induced delaminations have so far manifested themselves.

Delaminations have been found in a few specific wing panels on our CF-18s but these are believed to either have originated during manufacture or as a result of manufacture induced interlaminar stresses. Fig. 3 shows how poor fit-up where a wing rib butts against a spar can create a gap that allows the fasteners to pull down the skin producing localized bending and high interlaminar shear stresses. There are several factors that can combine to raise the level of these fit-up induced interlaminar stresses to the point where the material around the fastener holes delaminates. These include over-torquing of fasteners, use of a low modulus shim material such as nylon, a double row of rib fasteners, a laminate stacking sequence that significantly reduces the interlaminar shear strength and an intermediate laminate thickness. The latter exists because a thin skin can bend more readily to accommodate the step while a thick skin may have sufficient flexural stiffness to

Figure 3 . Localized bending and delamination caused by poor fit-up.

limit the pull down by the fasteners. In predicting the criticality of delaminations in monolithic carbon/epoxy laminates, analytical models based on both buckling and interlaminar fracture criteria have been used. However, the presence of fit-up stresses of unknown magnitude, as well as difficulty in quantifying the beneficial effects of fastener clamp-up have meant that such predictions have been used very conservatively.

ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION

The influence of both moisture and temperature on the properties of polymer matrix composites are generally taken into account during design. Typically, material property allowables are determined under room temperature/dry, cold/dry and hot/wet conditions. For the latter, a single "worst case" temperature and moisture content may be utilized in order to reduce the amount of testing required even though different parts of a structure will experience different maximum temperatures. While this approach has worked well for the most part, other more subtle forms of environmental degradation have been found to reduce the life of composite components. Of these, degradation of aramid/epoxy systems has probably been the most prevalent. Fig. 4 (a) shows a network of "trans-tow" cracks in an aramid/epoxy laminate made from woven fabric pre-preg. Both interfacial

Figure 4. Examples of transverse cracking in woven fabric aramid/epoxy laminates.

cracks, Fig. 4 (b) and longitudinal cracks in the fibres, Fig. 4 (c) show up clearly when sectioned at 45 degrees to the fibre direction and viewed under dark field illumination [1]. These cracks result primarily from the large difference between the radial and axial thermal expansion coefficients of aramid fibres [2]. In some systems, especially those cured at 180°C, the cracks appear on cooling down from the cure temperature while in others it may require exposure to low temperatures, thermal cycling or moisture absorption before they form. While, the short term mechanical properties may not be adversely affected, and in fact the peel strength may actually increase, the network of cracks allows moisture to pass rapidly through the laminate. This can

greatly reduce the life of sandwich panels made with honeycomb core since water can enter the cells where it can cause freeze/thaw damage. This mode of failure has been a particular problem with aircraft radomes [3]. Another form of environmental degradation that has occurred mostly in 120°C cured epoxy systems is a gradual breakdown or dissolution of the epoxy matrix. In the presence of moisture this manifests itself as a whitening of the surface and a tendency for the plies to peel apart. Fig. 5 shows the localized nature of the chemical breakdown. Although it is often difficult to fully establish the root cause of this type of degradation, susceptible matrices tend to be soft and have low glass transition temperatures which suggests that they have not been fully cured.

Figure 5. Dark field photomicrograph of the surface of an aramid/epoxy laminate showing light scattering from regions of matrix degradation. (45x)

This sensitivity to moisture was also found in an aramid/epoxy engine nacelle material that had suffered from dissolution of the matrix by leaking hydraulic fluid. This was in stark contrast to an adjacent co-cured ply of metallised glass fibres where the epoxy was still sound. This observation together with tests which showed little or no benefit of a post-cure suggest that the resin chemistry is to blame rather than an improper cure cycle. It is believed that high levels of moisture in the prepreg prior to cure, particularly in aramid/epoxy systems, may alter or inhibit the reaction of some curing agents and catalysts.

Moisture can degrade the properties of sandwich panels made with aluminum honeycomb core even in the absence of micro-cracks. Although it may take many years for it to diffuse through the face sheets, moisture will eventually reach the adhesive/aluminum interface where it can degrade the bond strength. Fig. 6 (a) shows that a single moisturizing/drying cycle can reduce the climbing drum peel strength of untreated core by over a factor of two. This loss in strength is accompanied by a change in failure mode from cohesive, in which the fillets remain attached to the

Figure 6. (a) Effect of moisturizing cycle on aluminum/adhesive peel strength. (b) Inner surface of 3-ply carbon/epoxy skin showing the adhesive mode of failure at the degraded interface.

core, to adhesive, in which the core is pulled cleanly out of the fillets as shown in Fig. 6(b), indicating that the bondline has been degraded. While in a sense this is a “metals” rather than a “composites” problem, it is the ability of the water to diffuse through the composite skin that allows it to reach the bondline, which is something that does not occur with a metal skin (unless exposed edges are present). A more expensive surface treated aluminum core can be used to prevent the problem. A true composites problem can arise during hot bonded repairs when moisture diffusion through composite face sheets can produce sufficient vapour pressure inside the core to debond the skin. This is discussed further below.

A more generic and surprisingly frequent form of degradation is that caused by overheating. While this can arise from accidental exposure to a number of different heat sources including engine exhaust gases and improperly controlled heating blankets during repair, it has also occurred because actual operating temperatures have exceeded the design temperature. Exposure to temperatures in excess of the cure temperature generally leads to a gradual degradation of the matrix dominated properties of thermoset composites. As the temperature is increased the time to initiate detectable damage drops off rapidly [4]. Paint discolouration and blistering generally give a good indication of the presence of thermal damage and the need for further inspection is limited to establishing when all of the damaged material has been removed i.e. defining the depth of the damage. New instruments are currently being developed to accomplish this [5]. From a maintenance point-of-view, environmental degradation of composites is often more pervasive than mechanical damage in as far as it is likely to produce fleet-wide problems rather than isolated cases. It is also clear that better screening tests need to be developed to identify potential problems before materials are qualified and put into production.

MAINTENANCE OPERATIONS

INSPECTION

There are two distinct requirements for non-destructive evaluation of composite structures once they are in service. Foremost is the need to quantify the extent of sub-surface damage at locations where impact damage is visible or suspected. Ultrasonic inspections either with hand held transducers or preferably with portable C-scan units provide sufficient information to assess and repair any damage that is present. The second requirement is for a rapid low cost method of periodically inspecting large areas of composite surfaces for sub-surface damage. The difficulty in adapting ultrasonics to scan large areas is that the transducer has to be manoeuvred over the entire surface keeping it in a more or less normal orientation. This problem can be avoided by using a laser beam to excite the ultrasonic wave at the surface and a second beam to detect the surface vibrations produced by the reflected signal. Development of commercial laser ultrasonic scanning systems has been carried out in Canada by Ultra-Optec Inc. Fig. 7 shows examples of the high resolution images that can be obtained [6]. While laser ultrasonics is better suited to depot level

Images courtesy of J-P Monchalin (NRC)

Figure 7. Time-of-flight (a) and amplitude (b) laser ultrasonic images of part of CF-18 wing skin showing stepped lap joint around fuel intake.

use, another Canadian technology provides an inexpensive means of quickly inspecting large composite surfaces for barely visible damage in the field. Based on an optical technique, D-SIGHT™ has been used in the automotive industry for over a decade to examine the surface

quality of both metallic and composite parts [7]. Although it cannot see below the surface it is extremely sensitive to surface imperfections and as a result can detect impact sites, localized bending due to fastener pull-down and near surface delaminations. Two D-SIGHT™ based systems developed specifically for use with aircraft are currently in use by the Canadian Forces. This technology may also prove valuable in enhancing the detectability of damage to composite aircraft certified for civilian use on the basis of close visual inspection, especially in light of the recent recognition that damage visibility decreases with time due to impact site relaxation [8].

PAINT REMOVAL

Composites are not generally amenable to the same paint removal techniques that have been employed for metals. Traditional chemical paint strippers that will remove epoxy primers tend to attack epoxy matrices as well. Grit blasting is too abrasive and cannot be controlled sufficiently to safely remove the coating without eroding the underlying composite. Research efforts aimed at finding a solution to this problem have covered a broad spectrum of alternative stripping methods including dry blasting with ice, dry ice (CO₂), various plastics and wheat starch, wet blasting with or without added abrasives as well as laser and flashlamp stripping. Faced with a requirement to have a paint removal system capable of completely stripping a CF-18 aircraft in operation by 1992, Canada opted for plastic media blasting and is currently in the process of qualifying wheat starch as a more environmentally friendly blasting media. Wheat starch, which has been developed as a blasting media in Canada by CAE Envirostrip™, is not only a renewable resource, but the spent starch is bio-degradable and easily separable from the paint residue [9]. Fig. 8 shows the high degree of precision with which a surface coating can be removed when a suitable blasting media is used under optimum blasting conditions. The original surface pattern produced by the peel ply is

Images courtesy of T. Foster (EDRD)

Figure 8. Scanning electron images of carbon/epoxy surfaces following coating removal showing (a) no damage and (b) removal of the surface matrix and some fibre damage.

still clearly visible. In contrast, Fig 8 (b) shows a surface from which all of the top layer of matrix has been removed allowing some fibre damage to occur. Ice blasting, which has been developed commercially in Canada by Ice Blast International is also an environmentally benign process and although slower at removing coatings, the comparatively soft ice particles are non-abrasive allowing the process to be used repeatedly at lower pressures for cleaning purposes.

It is currently considered necessary to carry out an extensive test program to ensure that the stripping process does not damage the surface plies or produce sub-surface delaminations. A typical test matrix includes flexure tests of fibre dominated laminates and tensile, compressive and fatigue testing of matrix dominated laminates (eg. $[\pm 22.5/\pm 67.5]_s$) as well as flatwise tension and flexural testing of sandwich panels and electron microscopy of the stripped surface. Qualification of new blasting parameters or a different media are therefore both time consuming and expensive. Some efforts have been made to model the blasting process and it is hoped that with further research it may eventually be possible to relate the blasting forces to the through thickness properties of the laminate and thereby reduce the need for such an extensive test matrix. At present there is no efficient means of removing paint from aramid/epoxy composites. Even at low

pressures, all blasting media tend to cause damage to the surface plies rather than removing the paint. When coatings have to be removed from aramid/epoxy components, it is being done by hand sanding, a process that is labour intensive and tends to fray the fibres and produce non-uniform removal.

BONDED PATCH REPAIR

Although bonded composite repairs are carried out on a routine basis, there are a number of fundamental issues related to their design, implementation and certification that are likely to continue to limit the severity of damage, laminate thicknesses and loading conditions to which they can be applied. On the CF-18, repairs involving adhesive bonding of pre-cured carbon/epoxy patches to the surface of the honeycomb sandwich structure are carried out in the field with few problems using commercially available heating blankets, temperature controllers and vacuum bagging. Damaged core material is routed out and a replacement plug of core spliced in place with a foaming adhesive. At the depot level, re-work of complex shaped components such as the main landing gear doors, are carried out using flexible core materials, pre-pregs and autoclave cures. The repair problem referred to previously, involving excessive vapour pressure developing within honeycomb core, illustrates some of the difficulties with elevated temperature bonded repairs. On the CF-18, part of the problem is that the epoxy film adhesive specified for bonded repair is the same as that used for the original bonding of the skins to the core. Although the 149°C cure temperature used for repair is 28°C lower than that during fabrication, it is still high enough to generate a significant vapour pressure and to produce creep in the skin/core adhesive. Degradation of the adhesive/aluminum bondline makes matters worse. Drying times to remove all of the absorbed moisture can run to several weeks and partial drying may actually exacerbate the situation since diffusion initially continues inwards down the existing moisture gradient. Thanks to recent improvements in epoxy resin chemistry, lower temperature (121°C) curing adhesives are now available that can provide the same elevated temperature properties as the original adhesive. However, when the impact of similar problems on higher service temperature composites such as bismaleimides are considered as well as the related problem of moisture diffusion out of solid laminates producing bondline porosity, it is clear that there is a real need for high T_g adhesives that can be cured at ambient temperature by some non-thermal process such as radiation curing [10].

For running loads greater than 0.6 kN/mm the load transfer into a bonded surface patch begins to exceed the capacity of most adhesives and/or that of the underlying surface plies of the composite. The latter is especially true on the CF-18 where the 2 outer plies are always at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the principal load direction. For typical aircraft laminates operating at moderate strain levels, single sided bonded patches are therefore limited to skin thicknesses of less than 3 mm. With greater thicknesses, higher strains or more orthotropic lay-ups double sided surface patches or scarf repairs are required. For sandwich components and many other types of aircraft structure, lack of access to the inside surface makes double sided patching impractical. The greatest drawback to scarf repairs is that the shallow scarf angles of 30:1 or less that are needed to reduce the adhesive shear stresses to the point where fatigue and creep are not a concern, dictate that large quantities of good material must be machined out in order to implement the repair. For example, for a 25 mm hole in a 5 mm thick skin, a scarf repair involves the removal of a volume of material 30 times greater than that of the original damage. As a result, the consequences of a weak or "kissing" bond are much more critical for a scarf repair than for an external patch. When the additional difficulties of implementing and inspecting scarf repairs are taken into account, the level of confidence required for approval of the repair procedure is often lacking. There are several alternative strategies that can be pursued in order to extend the applicability of one sided bonded patches without resorting to scarf repairs. Although not suitable for high strains, adding bolts to a bonded patch repair can increase the reliability and help counteract the peel stresses that become more troublesome as laminate thicknesses increase. Repairs in which the cleaned up damage is shaped to minimize the stress concentration and the edges of the cut-out are reinforced with a bonded doubler can also be quite effective as shown in Fig. 10. Repair schemes involving little or no clean-up of the material around a hole also deserve further consideration as often the strength reduction due to the original damage is significantly increased by the removal of the broken and delaminated material [11]. Problems that must be overcome with this approach are quantifying the structural significance of the damage and stabilizing the delaminations under compression loading. This discussion of bonded composite repairs has been intended to explain some of the limitations that currently exist and to indicate that there is still plenty of scope for improved repair materials and processes as well as innovative repair schemes.

Figure 10. Effectiveness of three different bonded repair schemes under tensile loading.

DELAMINATION REPAIR

There are three distinct repair options that can be considered for repairing delaminations: (i) removal of the delaminated material and installation of a patch; (ii) stabilization of the delaminated plies with mechanical fasteners; and (iii) injection of an adhesive into the delaminations. The first of these is normally used for honeycomb sandwich components because it is generally necessary to remove the delaminated skin before the associated damage to the underlying aluminum honeycomb can be repaired. The second option is effective up to moderate static strains levels but is not considered to be a long term solution. Resin injection is specified in the CF-18 Structural Repair Manual (SRM) for repairing delaminations in the monolithic carbon/epoxy components. However, Canadian experience with the specific repair that is described in the SRM is that it seldom works satisfactorily. Contributing to this are difficulties in mixing the resin without air entrapment, a short gel time, a relatively high viscosity and leakage of vacuum. An extensive investigation into the resin injection repair of delaminations in CF-18 carbon/epoxy laminates has led to the development of a much improved adhesive and a more reliable infiltration procedure [11-14]. Other findings of this work include:

- The compressive strength of impact damaged laminates can be fully restored provided there is no extensive back surface damage. Moreover, the resistance of the repaired region to subsequent impact is greater than that of the original undamaged laminate.
- Laminates containing delaminations similar to those created around fasteners as a result of fit-up stresses can be repaired to levels in excess of 100% of their original interlaminar shear strength.
- Contaminants that may have entered into delaminations before repair can be flushed out with a suitable solvent prior to resin injection without a significant reduction in the quality of the repair.

The effectiveness of these resin injection repairs may seem rather surprising in view of the fact that a fully cross linked ply interface is replaced by two weaker adhesively bonded interfaces, one on either side of the injected resin. However, in terms of interlaminar stresses and fracture toughness, there are several factors that have a positive effect. These include (i) the increase in the thickness of the region between the plies, (ii) the additional interleaving effect resulting from the use of a slightly tougher epoxy, (iii) the lower interlaminar thermal stresses that result from a cure temperature 40°C below that of the original laminate and (iv) the large surface area and mechanical interlocking that result from the "hackles" on the fracture surfaces. Fig. 11 shows a polished section through a typical repair. The gap between the delaminated plies is one of the key parameters controlling reparability as it not only affects the flow of resin into the delaminations but also determines the thickness of the resin layer. Infiltration tests on specimens designed to simulate the fastener hole delaminations described above revealed that the gap increases with

Figure 11. Section through a delamination repair.

Figure 12. (a) Effect of delamination size on the effectiveness of delamination repairs and the amount of delamination opening. (b) Repairability of impact damage and resistance to re-impact.

increasing delamination size, as shown in Fig. 12 (a), and decreases with increasing laminate thickness. One explanation for this dependency is that as delaminations form due to out of plane loading, the fracture surfaces momentarily move apart by an amount that increases in proportion to the out of plane compliance of the delaminated plies. Plastic deformation and fragments of matrix that break off during fracture limit the extent to which the gap can subsequently close. The results, shown in Fig. 12 (a), are for delaminations created under quasi-static loading conditions. Even so, there is a significant thickness effect and a small improvement in delamination resistance in the case of the largest opening. Under impact loading the gaps between the plies tend to be much larger and improvements in the compression after impact strength following repair can be as high as 30% as shown in Fig. 12 (b). From an operational point-of-view, impacts (like lightning) seldom strike the same spot twice and it is of course the compression strength after repair that is of primary interest. For strain levels up to 4000 micro-strain under both static loading (Fig. 12 (b)) and fatigue loading [11] resin injection repairs appear to provide a significant margin of safety. Fig. 13 shows a prototype resin injection device that has been used successfully to demonstrate the repair of impact damage on a salvaged CF-18 outer wing [11]. Whether or not it is possible to achieve

Lindahl Corporation, Vancouver, BC.

Figure 13. Prototype resin injection device developed for on-aircraft delamination repair.

similar results in less brittle systems, where the degree of inter-connectivity between the delaminations and the transverse shear cracks is likely to be less, has not been investigated. Thermoplastic matrix composites pose additional problems due to the inability of most adhesives to bond effectively without prior surface treatment. While delaminations in these materials can be repaired by fusing the surfaces back together, the high temperatures involved and the inability in most cases to support the back surface, limit this approach to parts with simple geometries that can be easily removed and placed in some form of tooling.

FUTURE LIFE CYCLE COST ISSUES

As composite materials continue to evolve and design approaches become more diverse and less conservative, the challenges involved in maintaining and supporting future composite structures will almost certainly increase. The use of more complex built-up structure, highly orthotropic stiffeners and post-buckled designs together with increased operating strains and higher service temperatures will undoubtedly stretch the limits of repairability. On the other hand, more insistent demands by end-users for greater supportability and lower life cycle costs will force composites designers to make full use of more damage resistant materials and material forms and to find innovative ways of protecting or locating highly loaded composite members away from sources of impact. While "visible damage" design criteria may eliminate the need to inspect large areas for sub-surface damage new methods will have to be found to quantify the extent to which visible surface damage may also have affected internal stiffeners and composite substructure. More attention will have to be paid to long term durability issues and better tools developed for predicting service life and life cycle costs. In addition, greater emphasis needs to be placed on accurately assessing the effect of damage on the remaining life of a structure and not just on the short term static strength. With usage of composites currently limited in many applications by trade-offs between better performance and higher acquisition costs it will only be by clearly demonstrating that composite components and structures can be built to last longer and have lower support costs that further gains will be made.

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DELAMINATION

